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**A new species of the genus *Pogonocherus* Dejean, 1821
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from China with a
redescription of poorly known *P. pilosipes* (Pic, 1907) as a
bases of a new subgenus *P.* (*Neopogonocherus* subgen. n.)**

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Gansu, Sichuan, China.

Abstract: *Pogonocherus* (s. str.) *paradimidiatus* sp. n. close to *P.* (s. str.)
dimidiatus Blessig, 1873 is described from China (Gansu and Sichuan
provinces). The distinguishing characters are discussed. *P.* (s. str.) *dimidiatus*
Blessig, 1873 is recorded from Gansu and Sichuan. A new subgenus is
proposed: *P.* (*Neopogonocherus* subgen. n.) with type species *Pogonocherus*
pilosipes Pic, 1907. *Pogonocherus* (*N.*) *pilosipes* (Pic, 1907) is redescribed.

Introduction

The genus *Pogonocherus* included only 3 Chinese species up to now. *P.* (*Pityphilus*) *fasciculatus* (DeGeer, 1775) distributed from Europe to Eastern Asia and 2 *Pogonocherus* (s. str.). *P.* (s. str.) *dimidiatus* Blessig, 1873 is very common in Russia (from Amur Region to Kuril Islands), all around Korean Peninsula and widely distributed in China to Sichuan Province southwards. *P.* (*Neopogonocherus* subgen. n.) *pilosipes* (Pic, 1907) is a poorly known species described after a single specimen from “Chine Orientale” without exact locality designation and sex determination. Two specimens of new species *Pogonocherus* (s. str.) *paradimidiatus* sp. n. described bellow were collected in Gansu and Sichuan by I. Belousov and I. Kabak in 2006 and 2012, one specimen was collected in Sichuan by S. Murzin in 2001.

Materials and methods

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 - 30.5 mm 1:2.8

- 4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustration were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.2.

Results

Pogonocherus (s. str.) *paradimidiatus* **sp. n.**

Figs 1-2

Three females only are available; body black, strongly attenuated posteriorly; head with very fine, short recumbent pubescence, without erect setae; frons slightly exposed, strongly transverse; genae wide, about as wide as width of lower eye-lobes; eyes strongly emarginated, about totally divided; the distance between dorsal eye-lobes a little more than apical width of the 1st antennal joint; antennae with numerous oblique setae; antennae reaching elytral apex; 1st antennal joint widened at middle; 2nd joint elongated; 2nd - 11th joints reddish basally; 4th joint half red; 3rd antennal joint about as long as 4th or a little shorter; 5th joint nearly 2 times shorter.

Prothorax transverse, about 1.25 times wider than long, as wide anteriorly as posteriorly, with large lateral tubercles; pronotum with a pair of oblique short central protuberances, depressed in the middle; scutellum semicircular, with black pubescence and contrast white stroke.

Elytra about 1.8 times longer than basal width with long outer apical spines typical for *Pogonocherus* (s. str.); internal angles of elytral apices totally obliterated; dorsal elytral surface with large irregular punctation along middle; large white transverse bend reaching epipleurae does not reach anterior elytral margin; a pair of central anterior tubercles with several short black setae; humeral and external elytral carinae anteriorly distinct; a pair of central elongated protuberances beyond the middle reddish, bear 2 or 3 black setae tufts each; elytral apices with bright white setae spots before apical spines.

Legs without erect setae; all tibiae with white setae bands and reddish bases.

Abdomen with exposed 5th visible sternite bearing deep small hollow near posterior margin.

Body length: 5.0-7.0 mm, width: 1.9-2.7 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is very close to *P.* (s.str.) *dimidiatus* Blessig, 1873 widely distributed in East Asia because of long elytral spines and bright white elytral band, but in *P. dimidiatus* white elytral band reaches anterior elytral margin; white small spots of fine setae scattered over elytra and legs; hollow of the last visible abdominal sternite in females is reduced to emargination of its posterior border.

P. (s. str.) *paradimidiatus* sp. n. is similar to European *P.* (s.str.) *hispidulus* (Piller, Mitterpacher, 1783), distributed to the East up to Orenburg Region, as white elytral band in *P. hispidulus* does not reach elytral bases; but elytral spines in *P. hispidulus* much shorter, hollow of the last visible abdominal sternite in females is reduced to emargination of its posterior border; internal angle of elytral apices well developed.

Another China species of *Pogonocherus* - *P. pilosipes* (Pic, 1907) is known on the bases of holotype and original description. It has strongly elongated pale-brown body similar to *P. perroudi* Mulsant, 1839, but without elytral setae tufts.

Type material. Holotype, female, China, Southern Gansu, NNW Kaba vill., 34°11'06"N, 103°22'52"E / 34°11'17"N, 103°22'49"E, 3640-3680 m, 15.06.2006, I. Belousov and I. Kabak leg. - author's collection; 2 paratypes: female, China, Northern Sichuan, WNW Jiuzhangou, 33°22'26"N, 103°48'08"E, 3320 m, 22.06.2012, I. Kabak leg. - author's collection; female, China, Sichuan prov., 40 km W Zhangla, 3600-3700 m, 12-14.7.2001, S. Murzin leg. - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow).

Additional material used for comparison.

Pogonocherus dimidiatus: 1 female (fig. 8), Gansu, SSW Woshar 3000 m 34°30'23"N, 104°49'48"E, 17.6.2005, S. Murzin leg. - author's collection; 1 female (fig. 7), S. Gansu, Tochizi, S. Wudu, 2400 m, 21-24.5.1997, S. Murzin leg. - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow); 1 male (fig. 5), Sichuan, W Heishui, 2500 m, 32°2'47.40"N, 103°1'0.48"E, 3-10.6.2012, S. Murzin leg. - author's collection; 1 male (fig. 6), Shaanxi, Zhouzhi, Taibaishan nat. park, 1350 m, 30.5.1999, M. Murzin leg. - collection of S. Murzin (Moscow); 1 ex., Primorsky Region, Kamenushka, 25.5.1992, S. Khvylya leg. - collection of V. Ustinov (Moscow); 1 ex., Primorsky Region, Kavalerovo, N. Luzhki 1.7.1997 - collection of

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V. Ustinov (Moscow); 1 male (fig. 3), Primorsky Region, Lazo, 9.5.2001, D. Kochetkov leg. - collection of M. Smirnov (Ivanovo); 28 specimens from the collection of Zoological Museum of Moscow State University (Moscow): 1 ex., Sibir or.; 4 ex., Primorsky Region, The upper reaches of the Lyanchikhe (new name Bogataya) River, 12.5.1947, from A. Kurentsova; 1 ex., Primorsky Region, Shkotovo, V-VI.1932; 1 ex., Suchansk distr., Freyzovka, from T. Samoylov; 2 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 30.5.1917, P. Elsky; ex., Ussuri, Okeanskaia, 4.6.1925; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 7.6.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 15.6.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 17.6.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 1.7.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 4.7.1917, P. Elsky; 2 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 6.7.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 8.7.1917, P. Elsky; 1 ex., Ussuri, Ossinovka, 6.9.1917, P. Elsky; 4 ex., Mandshuria, circ. Charbin, Siaolin, 5.5.1940, V. Alin; 1 ex., Japan, Sapporo, Tamanuki; 40 specimens from the collection of M. Danilevsky (Moscow): 1 male, 1 female, Primorsky Region, Gorno-Tayozhnaya Station, 19-20.7.1958, Filippov leg.; 1 male, Vladivostok; 4 males, 1 female, Vladivostok env. 26 km, 6.6.1958, Filippov leg.; 1 female, Primorsky Region, Ugolnaya Station, 27.5.1960, Anufriev leg.; 4 males, 5 females, Suchan [Partizansk] 10.6.1934; 5 males, 4 females, Khabarovsk env., Bychikha, 9.7.1975 ex larv. Aralia, M. Danilevsky leg.; 1 female (fig. 4), Khabarovsk env., Bychikha, 24.5.1976, Aralia, A. Kompantsev leg.; 1 female, Suputinsky Nat. Res. 22.5.1947; 2 males, 1 female, Sakhalin Is., Kholmsk Distr., Kalinino, 24.9.1984, M. Nesterov leg.; 1 female, Kunashir Is., Mendeleevo, 15.9.1976, A. Kompantsev leg.; 1 male, 1 female, Lyanchihe, 12.5.1947; 1 male, 3 females (fig. 9), South Korea (GW), Cheorwon-gun, Munhye-ri, 127.37°E / 38.17°N, 5.4.2010, S.H. Oh leg.; 1 male, Japan, Sapporo, Tamanuki leg.; 12 specimens from the collection of S. Murzin (Moscow): 3 males, 3 female, Primorsky Region, Kamenushka River, 15.6.1990, S. Khvylya leg.; 1 male, Primorsky Region, Suputinsky Nat. Res., 31.5.1969, M. Chernyakhovsky leg.; 3 males, 2 females, Primorsky Region, Ossinovka, 17.6.1917, P. Elsky leg.

Figs 1-2. *Pogonocherus* (s. str.) *paradimidiatus* sp. n.:

1 - Holotype, female; 2 - Paratype, female, China, Northern Sichuan, WNW Jiuzhangou, 33°22'26"N, 103°48'08"E, 3320 m, 22.06.2012, I. Kabak leg.

Figs 3-6. *Pogonocherus* (s. str.) *dimidiatus* Blessig, 1873: 3 - male, Primorsky Region, Lazo, 9.5.2001, D. Kochetkov leg. (photo by M. Smirnov); 4 - female, Khabarovsk env., Bychikha, 24.5.1976, Aralia, A. Kompantsev leg.; 5 - male, Sichuan, W Heishui, 2500 m, 32°2'47.40"N, 103°1'0.48"E, 3-10.6.2012, S. Murzin leg.; 6 - male, Shaanxi, Zhouzhi, Taibaishan nat. park, 1350 m, 30.5.1999, M. Murzin leg.

Figs 7-9. *Pogonocherus* (s. str.) *dimidiatus* Blessig, 1873: 7 - female, S. Gansu, Tochizi, S. Wudu, 2400 m, 21-24.05.1997, S. Murzin leg.; 8 - female, Gansu, SSW Woshar 3000 m 34°30'23"N, 104°49'48"E, 17.06.2005, S. Murzin leg.; 9 - female, South Korea (GW), Cheorwon-gun, Munhye-ri, 127.37°E / 38.17°N, 5.4.2010, S.H. Oh leg.

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Pogonocherus (*Neopogonocherus* **subgen. n.**)

Type species. *Pogonochaerus pillosipes* Pic, 1907

Diagnosis. The taxon is characterized by elongated body, elytra without setae tufts; elytral apices without spines, but roundly emarginated with distinct outer angles sharpened; female antennae longer than body; prothorax with big lateral tubercles sharpened apically; elytra without distinct transverse or onlique bands, but with diffused pale pubescent areas. All other known *Pogonocherus* have more or less distinct elytral setae tufts.

The new taxon includes a single Chinese species *P. (N.) pillosipes* (Pic, 1907).

Etymology. the name is composed of two words: Latin *neo* (new) and *Pogonocherus*; gender masculine.

Pogonocherus (*Neopogonocherus*) *pillosipes* (Pic, 1907)

Figs 10-11

Pogonochaerus pillosipes Pic, 1907: 21 [incorrect original spelling] - “Chine orientale”.

Pogonocherus (s. str.) *pillosipes*, Aurivillius, 1923: 332 - “Ostchina”; Winkler, 1929: 1210 - China orientalis; Hua, 1982: 112; Lin, Tavakilian, 2019: 361 - “China”; Danilevsky, 2020: 448 - “Chine orientale”.

Pogonocherus (s. str.) *pillosipes*, Plavilstshikov, 1926: 155, 161 - West-China [incorrect original spelling].

Ponogocherus (s. str.) *pillosipes*, Gressitt, 1951: 516 - “E.China” [misprint in the genus name; incorrect original spelling for species name].

Pogonocherus (*Eupogonocherus*) *pillosipes*, Breuning, 1963: 519 - Chine or.; 1975: 28 - Chine orientale.

Pogonocherus pillosipes, Hua, 2002: 225 (attribute to “Pic, 1923”) - China: E. China; Hua et al., 2009: 465 (attribute to “Pic, 1923”); Löbl, Smetana, 2010: 31 - “Chine orientale”.

Remark. *Pogonocherus pillosipes* (Pic, 1907) was a poorly known species. The holotype was never depicted before. A photo of the holotype-male (fig. 11) from Pic’s collection was kindly sent to me by G. Tavakilian.

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Pogonochaerus pilosipes n. sp. Modérément allongé, à peine brillant, fauve, en partie revêtu de pubescence grise avec les élytres faiblement mouchetés de brun foncé, sans fascicules pileux, orné de poils dressés plus ou moins longs, surtout sur les membres; antennes assez longues, testacées avec le sommet des articles courtement rembruni; prothorax court, à dent latérale saillante, orné sur le milieu du disque de 2 gibbosités saillantes, déprimé sur les parties antérieure et basale; écusson large, pubescent de gris; élytres un peu plus larges que le prothorax, à épaules marquées, mais arrondis, progressivement atténués postérieurement, tronqué-échancrés au sommet avec l'angle externe assez saillant en pointe, un peu déprimés sur leur milieu et ornés sur les côtés de 2 côtes distinctes étendues presque de la base au sommet, à coloration générale fauve avec une vague fascie grisâtre oblique placée avant le milieu; pattes moyennes, testacées, hérissées de longs poils clairs. Long. 8 millimètres, Chine Orientale (coll. Pic).

Ressemble un peu à *Perroudi* Muls., forme plus allongée, élytres dépourvus de fascicules pileux, etc.

Fig. 10. Original description of *Pogonochaerus pilosipes* Pic, 1907.

Body relatively narrow, attenuated posteriorly, covered by dense, brownish recumbent pubescence, with numerous pale long erected setae; antennae much longer than body, reaching elytral apices by 8th joint; joints 1-3 dark brown, other joints reddish-brown, darkened apically; 4th antennal joint is the longest, longer than 1st; 3rd joint shorter than 1st; 3rd and 4th joints with very long erected pale setae.

Prothorax about as wide anteriorly as posteriorly, about 1.2 times shorter than basal width; with anterior and posterior constrictions; with big lateral tubercles; pronotum with a pair of central carinae; scutellum small, transverse, with pale-grey pubescence.

Elytra about 2 times longer than basal width; with numerous pale erect setae and wide lateral yellowish stripes, without elytral setae tufts (a unique character in the genus); yellowish oblique stripes are situated before middle and near apices; very narrow dark-brown short strokes are distinct at middle; elytral apices with shallow emargination, with distinct outer angles, but without spines.

Legs also with numerous pales, long erect setae, with strongly clavate femora; apical joint of posterior tarsi longer than 2nd-3rd joints combined.

Body length: 7.5 mm.

Material. Holotype, male with a label: “Chine Orient. / (ou Tonkin ?)” - Pic’s collection (Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris).

Taxonomy remark. The genus *Pogonocherus* Dejean, 1821 (type species: *Cerambyx hispidus* Linnaeus, 1758) was traditionally regarded consisting of two subgenera: the nominative and subgenus *Pityphilus* Mulsant, 1862 (type species: *Cerambyx ovatus* Goeze, 1777). Subgenus *Pogonocherus* s. str. was characterized by elytral epical spines, while in subgenus *Pityphilus* Mulsant, 1862 elytral apices were rounded or truncated, but without spines. In reality this division was not exact as several species demonstrated intermediate situation and were arbitrary placed to one subgenus or another. For example, *P. sturanii* Sama, Schurmann, 1982 with emarginated elytral apex and distinct outer apical elytral angle was accepted by Vives, Alonso-Zarazaga (2000) in *P.* (s. str.), while *P. ehdenensis* Sama, Rapuzzi, 2000 with about same elytral apex was placed to *Pogonocherus* (*Pityphilus* Muls.) by Cocquempot et al. (2016). That is why many of modern authors gave up the divisions of *Pogonocherus* into subgenera (Sama, 2003; Hasegawa, 2007; Miroshnikov, 2009; Löbl, Smetana, 2010). While others accept two subgenera up to now (Vives, Alonso-Zarazaga, 2000; Vitali et al., 2011; Shapovalov, 2012; Cocquempot et al., 2016; Doychev et al., 2017; Lin, Yang, 2019; Danilevsky, 2020). Sometimes both subgenera were upgraded to genus rank (Villiers, 1978; Bílý, Mehl, 1989).

Here I accept three subgenera; 4 species with truncated (or feebly emarginated) elytral apices must be included in subgenus *Pityphilus* Mulsant, 1862: *P. (Pityphilus) ehdenensis* Sama & Rapuzzi, 2000; *P. (Pityphilus) ovatoides* Rapuzzi & Sama, 2014; *P. (Pityphilus) resslii* Holzschuh, 1977; *P. (Pityphilus) sturanii* Sama & Schurmann, 1982.

Note. Wang (2014: 983) used the name “*Pogonocherus pilosipes* Pic, 1923” for another depicted taxon (without lateral thoracic tubercles), which does not belong to the genus *Pogonocherus*.

Fig. 11. *Pogonocherus (Neopogonocherus) pilosipes* (Pic, 1907):
Holotype, male (photo by G. Tavakilian).

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